

On the Behaviour of Bismuth Fluoride as a Guest Component in the Study of Uptake by Calcium and Rare-earth Fluorides

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Distribution study with calcium fluoride and cerous fluoride as hosts and RaE as guest, reveals that both the hosts take up bismuth tracer through mixed crystal formation. Study has been extended from the tracer level to the finite scale of the guest component. It has been argued that some of the compounds of bismuth show some morphological analogy with those of the rare-earths and presence of bismuth in calcium fluoride lattice can be expected from such study.

From morphological point of view it has been observed that bismuth shows certain analogy with rare earth compounds¹, and such analogy is not unexpected in view of the ionic size of the bismuth ion. Certain calcium compounds like calcium fluoride, calcium oxalate etc., have been found to be mixed crystal forming with the corresponding rare earth compounds^{2,3,4}. Size of the calcium ion is probably responsible for such behaviour. It is therefore expected that bismuth also would show some analogy as guest components towards the calcium fluoride and cerous fluoride. With this object in view the co-separation study, as mentioned in the title, was undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents like calcium chloride, hydrochloric acid, ammonium acetate, cerium compounds etc. were all of analar variety. RaE in equilibrium with RaD was procured from Messrs. Philips Duphar. Carrier free RaE was separated from its mother by the following procedure. A solution containing RaD in equilibrium with its daughter in nitric acid medium was taken in a beaker. A few milligrams of lead nitrate was added and the solution was evaporated to dryness to drive off nitric acid. Evaporation was repeated several times after addition of water. Finally lead nitrate was washed out with water. On removing lead nitrate as mentioned, RaE adsorbed presumably on the glass surface, was recovered by boiling with concentrated nitric acid. The recovery was about 85 per cent and the product was practically free from any solid matter. But it should not be claimed to be free from Po²¹⁰. Presence of Po²¹⁰ however does not play any role in the distribution measurement of RaE by liquid counter. Description of a typical experiment will clarify the procedure adopted for finding out the partition factor. A solution of the host component, say calcium chloride was taken in a beaker. Hydrofluoric acid of known concentration was added from a calibrated pipette. The mineral acid was neutralised by addition of ammonium acetate under constant stirring. pH of the medium was maintained

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between 3 and 4. The filtrate was pipetted out with a pipette having a filterpaper cap at the end and the activity left in solution was measured with a glass wall counter meant for measuring liquids. It should be pointed out that the slow neutralisation of mineral acid by addition of ammonium acetate was found necessary for avoiding formation of colloidal calcium fluoride. In case of cerous fluoride however mineral acid concentration was retained about 2N with respect to nitric acid. Amount of fluoride precipitated was computed from the amount of hydrofluoric acid added assuming that at such high concentration fluorides of the host components were practically insoluble. D and λ values are calculated from the following expressions and results are given in tables.

$$\left(\frac{\text{Tracer}}{\text{Carrier}} \right)_{\text{in solid}} = D \left(\frac{\text{Tracer}}{\text{Carrier}} \right)_{\text{in solution.}}$$

$$\log \left(\frac{\text{Initial tracer}}{\text{Tracer in solution}} \right) = \lambda \log \left(\frac{\text{Initial carrier}}{\text{Carrier in solution}} \right)$$

TABLE I

On the study of the Heterogeneous Distribution Factor (λ) in Acid Insoluble Fluoride Systems. Period of shaking— 5 minutes.

% of the host component in question separated.	% of the guest component in question carried.	λ values	D-values	Comments
1 (a) CaF ₂	RaE			
18.40	40.2	2.53	2.96	1 (a). With carrier free RaE at room temperature (≈ 30°C) at pH 3 to 4
29.84	56.7	2.36	3.08	
36.80	66.3	2.97	3.38	
48.23	82.4	2.64	5.03	
		Average	2.47	
1 (b). CaF ₂	RaE			
18.40	38.9	2.42	2.82	1 (b). With finite concentration of bismuth at room temperature (≈ 30°C) at pH 3 to 4. Molarity of bismuth:—1.3 × 10 ⁻⁴ M.
29.84	57.6	2.42	3.19	
36.80	68.2	2.50	3.68	
48.23	81.6	2.57	4.76	
		Average	2.48	
2 (a). CeF ₃	RaE			
61.7	21.3	0.25	0.17	2 (a). With carrier free RaE at room temperature (≈ 34°C) in 2N HNO ₃ medium.
74.0	28.5	0.25	0.14	
86.9	32.2	0.19	0.07	
92.5	48.0	0.25	0.07	
		Average	0.24	
2 (b). CeF ₃	RaE			
61.6	18.2	0.21	0.14	2 (b). With finite concentration of bismuth at room temperature (≈ 30°C) in 2N HNO ₃ medium. Molarity of bismuth:—1.3 × 10 ⁻⁴ M
73.9	27.1	0.24	0.13	
86.9	36.2	0.22	0.09	
92.4	43.9	0.22	0.06	
		Average	0.22	

Initial concentration of the host components; (1) Concentration of calcium: 1.8 × 10⁻³M.; (2) Concentration of cerium (ous): 6.3 × 10⁻³M.

TABLE II

On the Study of the Time Required for the Attainment of Equilibrium in internally formed Acid Insoluble Fluoride systems at 35°C.

Time in hours	% of the host component precipitated.	% of the guest component carried	D	Comments
1.	CaF ₂	RaE		1. With carrier free RaE at pH 3 to 4.
24	18.4	33.6	2.24	
48	18.4	37.1	2.62	
72	18.4	31.3	2.02	
96	18.4	34.8	2.37	
2.	CeF ₃	RaE		2. With carrier free RaE in 2N HNO ₃ medium.
24	86.9	64.5	0.27	
48	86.9	63.2	0.26	
72	86.9	66.5	0.30	
96	86.9	63.2	0.26	

Initial concentration of the host components, (1) Concentration of calcium:— 1.8×10^{-1} M; (2) Concentration of cerium (ous):— 6.3×10^{-2} M.

TABLE III

On the Study of the Homogeneous Distribution Factor (D) in Acid Insoluble Fluoride systems at 35°C. Period of shaking—4 days.

% of the host component in question separated.	% of the guest component in question carried.	D	λ	Comments.
1. CaF ₂	RaE			1. With carrier free RaE at pH 3 to 4.
18.4	34.8	2.37	2.10	Initial concentration of calcium: 1.8×10^{-1} M.
29.8	51.1	2.46	2.02	
36.8	63.5	2.99	2.20	
		Average	2.10	
2. CeF ₃	RaE			2. With carrier free RaE in 2N HNO ₃ medium.
61.7	39.9	0.41	0.53	Initial concentration of cerium(ous):— 6.3×10^{-2} M.
74.0	50.1	0.35	0.52	
86.9	63.2	0.26	0.49	
92.5	71.3	0.20	0.48	
		Average	0.51	

A glance at table-I will show that the heterogeneous distribution factor λ comes out constant in the case of uptake of RaE with calcium fluoride and cerous fluoride as the hosts. This is true in case of tracer level as well as in finite concentration of the guest component (bismuth). Conclusion can therefore be arrived at that calcium fluoride and cerous fluoride take up RaE through mixed crystal formation. The internally formed

host components were equilibrated for four days in the conventional way, keeping the extent of precipitation the same, when practically no change in the extent of uptake of the guest with respect to period of equilibration (vide Table-II) was found. It has been further observed that on prolonged equilibration of the internally formed system (vide table-III) the distribution remains heterogeneous. The heterogeneous distribution factor (λ) in case of both the hosts remains constant (vide table-III) though the values differ from those obtained under rigorous experimental conditions of examining heterogeneous distribution constancy (vide table-I). The difference in λ - values is due to the difference in the experimental conditions⁵. Constancy of the heterogeneous distribution factor in place of homogeneous distribution coefficient gives an evidence that the rate of diffusion and recrystallisation in the system under consideration is a very slow process. It is well-known that calcium fluoride contains traces of rare earths and our study with bismuth as the guest gives a strong evidence that rare earth analogue like bismuth will also be present in calcium fluoride. Before conclusion it should be pointed out that such study gives some light on the morphological analogy of bismuth and rare earths and it also helps us to predict the presence of rare elements in minerals.

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